

ISic0829

I.Sicily inscription 0829

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list of

priests

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dum esset sacerdos Syriae deae
2. Tiberius Tiberii f(ilius)
3. pontifex fil(ius) Dapsili
4. Amphilobi vero Paeadia qui fuit Theodori qui fuit
5. Morrecini qui iusta fecere
6. praesides Syriae deae singulis annis
7. P(ublius) plonus P(ubli) filius
8. M(arcus) Pomponius di[---]
9. L(ucius) Lucinius [---]
10. L(ucius) Octavius L[---]
11. T(itus) Phaecius [---]
12. Attale [---]
13. Eutich[---]

Apparatus

Text after IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492453

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PHI 140299

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0009 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5372

Tusa, V. 1963. L'anfipolia a Solunto. *Kokalos*. 9: 185-194. At 189

Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 300 with n.102

Sfameni Gasparro, G. 1973. I culti orientali in Sicilia. Leiden. At 162-164 no.358

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